

Patterns to address trusted data sharing and to implement modern data access

→ **Author:** Joao Rodrigues Frade (European Commission)

→ **Contact:** joao.rodrigues-frade@ec.europa.eu

Track relevant to this submission:

→ **Special Track 11:** Recent experiences using GovTech to address data sharing challenges and to implement modern data access paradigms

Alternative track relevant to this submission:

→ **Standard Track:** Systems & Infrastructure

Introduction

Background

We live in an era of increasing connectivity and accelerating change. For example, in Europe, the ongoing digital transformation will most likely lead to the full digitisation of the paperwork necessary for the free movement of goods, services, capital and people within the European single market. Consequently, the numerous paper documents with official value, e.g. printed on paper or plastic cards, will no longer have a physical existence, as they too will become digital.

This paper discusses the implications and challenges associated to the digitisation of paper documents issued by government entities with official value. As government and its services become digital, the well-established in-person verification processes reliant on these documents will also change. Even if it is safe to say that, in the future, official documents and associated checks will become digital by default, the way to do it is not obvious and it is difficult to know how long the transition period will last and how many intermediate points there will be.

One thing is for sure, this transformation represents a great opportunity for society. Ultimately, once completed, this transition will ultimately lead to faster and cheaper online verification processes with the same level of trust, or even higher, than everyday traditional paper-based checks.

Key takeaways

The paper will explain:

- The challenges associated to the digital transformation of public administrations and, more in particular, the challenges associated to the digitisation of documents with official value;
- Two key patterns to share data in a trusted way using the analogy of the digital postal office and of the digital wallet. This paper will compare both patterns and draw some considerations about how they may contribute to the ongoing digital transformation. Of course that these are not the only patterns to share data with sensitive or official nature but they will provide a good example of the different concepts at play on how to ensure trust in data and documents in an increasingly digital environment.
- The emerging concept of verifiable credentials associated to blockchain technology. The paper will also explain how Europe is currently embracing this new technology by creating the European Blockchain Services Infrastructure (EBSI), a government-driven Pan-European blockchain infrastructure.

Fundamental patterns for data sharing

Why do we trust paper

Governmental entities are important intermediaries of many transactions happening in our society as the documents they issue, or certify, are a common way to verify information about people (identity cards, work permits, driving licenses, etc.) and goods (origin of containers, safety of products, etc.). Official documents inherit the trust deposited in the entities that issue them and become key **trust facilitators** among the many players transacting in the single market, both within and across borders. The digitisation of official documents opens up the possibility of faster flows of information since it becomes possible to automate the verification of information. However, this transformation is not straightforward as digital documents are extremely easy to duplicate and to modify. This explains why digital trust is becoming a major challenge for the removal of in person and other types of offline checks. In short, the challenge is much bigger than to digitise documents and to share them over the internet. The challenge is how to make the transition from traditional paper-based checks to digital verifications, in a trusted way. This paper will not discuss or explain the European initiatives at regulatory level supporting this transition. The creation of an EU-wide regulatory framework fit for the digital age is of crucial importance to the future of the European digital economy as it creates regulatory certainty for online transactions happening within a Member State and, as importantly, across borders. This regulatory framework is being created sector by sector and through overarching legislation such as the General Data Protection Regulation¹, the eIDAS regulation² or the Single Digital Gateway³ regulation.

How to move beyond paper

While the European regulatory framework is being shaped and implemented to allow us moving beyond paper, an important discussion is happening at a more technical level about how share these digital documents, also referred to '**official documents**', '**evidences**' or '**credentials**' in a trusted way.

The "**just in time evidence issuance**" pattern has been the most common way, in the last decades, to share sensitive data or data with an official value via electronic means. This pattern fundamentally relies on the 'just in time' fulfilment of a requests for information made directly to its authentic source such as a population register, a vehicles register or a business register. A good analogy for this pattern is the digital post.

The recent advent of blockchain has led to the raise of an alternative pattern, known as "**verifiable credentials**". Blockchain is often times misunderstood as (yet) another data sharing protocol i.e. just another technology to share information but distributed. The next chapters will show that this premise is flawed because several data exchange protocols already existed before blockchain that enabled distributed information sharing at scale. That is not new. Blockchain is not a protocol for sending and receiving data but a shared ledger where the blocks of information compositing it contain permanent and variable records about specific entities. For example, blockchain creates an immutable and decentralized record of logs of financial transactions, the lifecycle of a document, the steps in a supply chain, etc. In practical terms, this means that blockchain can facilitate checks on the integrity, origin, etc. of official documents without the need to contact their issuing entity each time.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection/data-protection-eu_en

² <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/trust-services-and-eid>

³ https://ec.europa.eu/growth/single-market/single-digital-gateway_en

PATTERN 01 - Just in time evidence issuance, the “digital postal office”

What is the pattern about?

At conceptual level, this model is similar to a traditional paper flow with the post office as the key intermediary. Below is an example:

- When someone is required to prove something (e.g. nationality) as part of an administrative process (e.g. registration of a new-born);
- This person is typically asked to request the entity managing the authentic source of information (e.g. the population register) to issue an official document that demonstrates this (e.g. a birth certificate);
- Even when the request for the birth certificate can already be done online, its fulfilment is often times still carried out offline with the delivery of a paper document by post.

When transferring this flow into the digital world, this means that the authentic sources of information must connect to a **digital postal office**:

- Have a way to identify themselves digitally and also to verify the identity of requesters of information (e.g. using digital certificates) as **digital identification** is central to data sharing;
- Have a way to receive requests in digital format via a **secure channel** (e.g. using a data exchange protocol) that ensures **data integrity**;
- Issue the digital document (or data) in real-time and
- Send it back to the requester, or an entity on its behalf, through the same secure channel in digital format (ensuring its integrity and **confidentiality**).

How does the pattern work?

For several decades, data exchange protocols have been evolving from EDI, to the AS2 protocol and the more advanced protocols based on secure web-services, such as AS4⁴, that use digital certificates and encryption to protect the data. Independently of the security features, all of them follow the logic of the digital postal office combined with trusted digital entities. Here is how it works:

- Assuming that the exchange is carried out over the internet, a **secure information exchange protocol** is adopted by the entities wanting to share data with each other to ensure its integrity and confidentiality. This protocol usually predefines key attributes at “envelope” level such as who is the sender, who is the receiver, what is exchanged, etc. This metadata is very similar what we find on a letter in the paper-world;

⁴ <https://www.iso.org/standard/79109.html>

- The actual document or data is usually referred to as “payload” (i.e. the content of the letter) which can also be subject to standardisation, both its semantics and format, as this typically enables further automation;
- Before starting to share data, both the data requester and the data provider need to acquire electronic certificates that uniquely identify them (e.g. using a PKI). Alternatively, an intermediary can do it on their behalf. This means that the envelope is signed and timestamped before being shared. This signature also ensures that the data is not changed while being exchanged (i.e. its integrity);
- Furthermore, to ensure confidentiality, i.e. that only the addressee can open the envelope, data can also be encrypted;
- Upon concluding the process of setting-up a trusted communication channel, the entities have the infrastructural elements in place to:
 - trust each other’s identities (thanks to the PKI solution) and
 - the integrity of the information they receive from each another (thanks to the data exchange protocol);
- For additional security, the exchanged documents or data (i.e. “the payload”), can also be signed upon issuing to ensure that their origin and integrity is verifiable beyond the moment of exchange.

This pattern relies on an IT infrastructure with high-availability and security, in addition to suitable monitoring and governance arrangements. The automated exchanges of information described above are therefore most likely to happen between governmental entities (G2G) playing the role of Sender and Receiver. If this is the case, the request for information to an ‘authentic data source’ happens following:

- the identification of a citizen (natural person) or a business (legal person);
- with their consent.

A digital identification framework, covering both citizens and businesses, is a crucial prerequisite for this pattern to work. To make it an end-to-end solution, secure mailboxes and other eGov solutions, such as eGov portals, have to be connected to this type of digital post solution. It is also important to note that the participation of the GovTech ecosystem is essential as this provides ample choice of solutions to government and it accelerates the creation of complementary added-value services.

PATTERN 02 - Verifiable Credentials, “the digital wallet”

What is the pattern about?

At conceptual level, this model is similar to a wallet of documents. However, instead of verifications through physical checks, these are now possible using digital means thanks to cryptography and blockchain technology. In this pattern, official documents (or credentials) are fundamentally a set of claims about someone or something. The verifiable credential can contain claims about the citizen having a given nationality, holding a certain degree, etc. These claims are then:

- minted in a digital document, usually known as a verifiable credential;
- confirmed by a competent authority using electronic signatures.

Furthermore, cryptographic hashes could be recorded on a blockchain alongside with the status of the Verifiable Credential. It is important to highlight that, due to performance and data privacy concerns, the blockchain should not store the data itself. Once these steps are completed, this will enable the data to be verified at any time using cryptographic methods. The data and documents

can at this point be stored in a **digital wallet** by the citizen or organization i.e. the Holder of information. The citizen can then create a verifiable presentation, containing data from one or several credentials, as supporting evidence to real-life transactions such as changing address, applying for a job, etc. Verification processes are possible to automate, below are a few examples:

- The hash of the document itself (i.e. to verify the integrity of information);
- The Issuer (i.e. to verify the issuer of the official document) and
- The Holder (i.e. to verify to whom the official document was issued to).

How does the pattern work?

Pattern 02 Verifiable Credentials

The above diagram shows that, unlike the first pattern, any Verifier checking the authenticity of a digital document (a.k.a. a verifiable presentation) can rely on cryptographic verifications without needing to contact its Issuer. Furthermore, it is typically up to the Holder of the document to share it with the Verifier. This means that the Holder controls the information that it wants to share with others. Furthermore, selective disclosure of information may also be possible when information is standardized and advanced cryptographic methods, such as Zero-Knowledge Proofs, are used. Similar to the previous pattern, verifiable credentials depend on several infrastructural elements:

- The first element is, without any surprise, a fully functioning, permissioned, but publicly available, blockchain network that can be trusted by European public administrations. This involves, among other things, strong governance arrangements and security controls;
- Similar to the previous pattern, a digital identification framework is again a crucial prerequisite for this pattern to work. In a typical blockchain paradigm, this means that every public administration, business and citizen would need to get a “decentralized ID” (DID) according to Self-Sovereign Identity principles. DIDs are a new type of identifier that enable verifiable, decentralized digital identity.
- As DIDs say nothing about the actual person or organization associated to it, a scalable solution is needed to link DIDs reliably to their associated ‘legal’ entity;
- Finally, citizens and businesses would need to have a trusted and secure digital wallet, connected to the blockchain, to hold their DID and documents.

The European Commission and the Member States are currently working on a Pan-European initiative, the European Blockchain Services Infrastructure (EBSI⁵) to address the above challenges both at technical and legal level. As this pattern tries to bring greater data control to citizens and businesses over their data, the participation of the GovTech ecosystem is even more crucial than in the previous pattern. Once all the infrastructural elements are in place, their participation can greatly accelerate the dissemination of emerging tech in everyday applications connecting governments to their citizens. This is likely to take some time and require incentives in this direction.

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/cefdigital/wiki/display/CEFDIGITAL/ebsi>

Final thoughts

The conclusions of this paper are organised in three themes:

Prerequisites

For information sharing to be trusted, **there are important prerequisites that need to be in place** such as a legal and technical framework for trusted digital identities and electronic signatures. These technologies are used in both patterns as a way for public administrations, businesses and citizens to identify themselves and prove that they are who they say they are. The good news is that these prerequisites are already covered by the eIDAS Regulation, the legal basis for one single EU-wide framework for eID and trust services. This important regulation not only promotes digital services that are more secure but it also ensures that these services work across borders within the EU. Furthermore, eIDAS also provides a common legal framework for the creation of digital postal services that work across borders.

Complementarity

The second conclusion to be drawn is that new solutions continue to emerge to support the creation of trust when sharing data in the digital economy. This is of course essential when governments share sensitive data and/ or data with an official value. In this sense, it is important to highlight that the patterns described in this paper are not at odds with each other. These patterns are **complementary** as both of them enable transactions to be carried out (fully) online without the need for physical checks. Both patterns are part of a modern eGov digital infrastructure. This means that digital postal offices will be able to connect and benefit from a blockchain infrastructure and its associated digital wallets, and the other way around. The main challenge will therefore be for governments to have a good understanding of both patterns so that they can apply them in their digital infrastructure in an efficient and effective way to achieve goals such the once only principle⁶ or a proactive digital public administration.

Ecosystem

Finally, these patterns also show that innovative technologies, such as blockchain and Verifiable Credentials, will **enable more control by citizens over their data** (sometimes named 'data sovereignty' or 'self-sovereign identity'). However, the diffusion of such emerging technologies will require a strong impulsion both by governments, in particular when it comes to providing clear answers to privacy concerns and legal compliance, and the GovTech ecosystem, for making everyday applications that are secure and easy to use. Since the advent of the internet, engaging innovation ecosystems have become an essential element for the diffusion of new technologies in society. The engagement strategy should therefore be outlined both by governments at national level as part of their digital strategy as well as at EU level through its Shaping Europe's digital future initiative⁷ and the upcoming Digital Europe Programme⁸.

⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/cefdigital/wiki/display/CEFDIGITAL/Once+Only+Principle>

⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en>

⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/europe-investing-digital-digital-europe-programme>